

Main interview questions

1. Can you describe your experience as an elite athlete during your school years? How did it influence your daily life and education?
2. Could you talk about how you felt when you first entered university as a retired elite athlete?
3. How did your sports training experience help or hinder your academic learning?
4. Did you experience any challenges in managing academic tasks or responsibilities during your time at university? If so, could you describe them and how you dealt with them?
5. How did you manage the balance between your academic responsibilities and the habits developed during your sports career?

Notes: all interviews were conducted in Chinese to obtain the participants' more precise responses.